

Board Financial Expertise and Financial Reporting Quality of Listed Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria Moderated by Firm Size

BELLO Adamu Lawal

National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) Kaduna, Nigeria
adamulbello@gmail.com

OKPANACHI Joshua

Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria
okpasmg82@gmail.com

NYOR Terzungwe

Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria
tnyor@nda.edu.ng

JOSHUA Samuel Gambo

Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria from 2003 to 2022. The study also used one dependent variable (financial reporting quality), one independent variable (board financial expertise), one moderating variable (firm size) and two control variables (firm age and board size). This study adopted longitudinal research designs, which involve collecting data from the same individuals or groups over an extended period. The population and the sample size had the same number of 10 listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study used secondary data and panel regression technique for the analysis. The result for board expertise as moderated by firm size indicate that the coefficient has negative significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. In conclusion, in larger firms, the positive effect of board financial expertise on financial reporting quality may be mitigated or even reversed. Based on these findings, the study recommended that, given the moderating effect of firm size, companies should conduct periodic governance audits, focusing on the effectiveness of financial expertise in relation to firm size.

Keywords: Board financial expertise, Firm size, Financial reporting quality, Board size, Board age

Wordcount: 142

1. Introduction

Ensuring transparency and reliability of financial information provided to stakeholders is crucial, and high-quality financial reporting plays a significant role in achieving this goal

(Akeju & Babatunde, 2017). Researchers in the accounting field and related disciplines have been concerned about the quality of financial reporting in the past decade, aiming to understand the production of unbiased financial reports (Rasha, 2017; Fung, 2014; Ivanova & Bikeeva, 2016; Nyor, 2013; Mahboub, 2017). Companies have an obligation to prepare relevant financial reports that enable users to make informed decisions (Asegdew, 2016; Fathi, 2013). Maintaining high-quality reporting benefits firms by potentially reducing debt expenses and increasing stock prices (Savina, 2016; Soheilyfar et al., 2014).

In the context of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria, the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality is particularly crucial. Historical financial scandals involving companies like Enron, Satyam, Lehman Brothers, and others demonstrate that management does not always provide an true picture of a company's financial standing (Markham, 2015). The issue of financial reporting quality has gained attention not only among users but also in the broader economy due to its significant influence on economic decisions (Markham, 2015; Tihamiyu, & Oyedokun, 2019).

Given the importance of the oil and gas industry in Nigeria's economy, the financial reporting practices of listed companies in this sector have far-reaching implications for stakeholders. Many scholars have recently emphasized improving financial reporting quality to reduce information asymmetry and enhance market transparency. For developing economies like Nigeria, the truth and good faith of financial reports are crucial to provide reliable information to shareholders, investors and other stakeholders. Yet, financial fraud is still prevalent, which may negatively impact stakeholders' decision-making. Thus, various accounting laws and regulations have been implemented to prevent fraudulent activities, although auditors might not have absolute control over them (Ogundajo, Odunayo, Osunsusi, Desi, & Oyedokun, 2023; Hanh et al., 2024). This study focuses on the board financial expertise of companies as it is closely tied to the disclosure of high-quality financial reports. The composition and expertise of a company's board of directors, particularly in financial matters, play a vital role in ensuring accurate and reliable financial reporting.

The contemporary business environment is characterized by complex financial structures and regulatory frameworks, demanding a nuanced understanding of financial reporting practices. In the context of the Nigerian oil and gas sector, where economic significance is underscored by a multitude of factors, the scrutiny on financial reporting quality becomes

paramount. Within this milieu, the role of corporate governance mechanisms, particularly the financial expertise of the board, assumes a critical position in shaping the transparency and reliability of financial disclosures.

Board financial expertise refers to the knowledge, skills, and experience of board members in financial matters, including accounting, auditing, and financial analysis. Board members with financial expertise play a crucial role in determining the quality of financial reporting (Oyedokun, Okwuosa, & Isah, 2019; Ashafoke et al., 2021). Their financial skills and experience enable them to have a deeper understanding of accounting issues, make informed decisions, and enhance the financial reporting process (Ashafoke et al., 2021). It is expected that a board with sufficient financial expertise can provide effective oversight and improve the quality of financial reporting. However, the impact of board financial expertise on financial reporting quality may vary depending on the size of the company especially in the oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

While prior studies (Ashafoke et al., 2021; Shamaki et al., 2023; Suleiman et al., 2020) have explored the relationship between board characteristics and financial reporting quality, there is a gap in understanding how firm size moderates board financial expertise and financial reporting quality of listed Nigerian oil and gas industry. This study, therefore, examines how board financial expertise effect financial reporting quality across companies of different sizes, with firm size acting as a moderating variable.

The inclusion of firm age and board size as control variables in this study strengthens its internal validity by accounting for potential confounding factors. By controlling these variables, the study aims to enhance the precision of the findings regarding the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality in the specific context of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. For instance, the age of a firm often reflects its level of experience within the industry. In the oil and gas sector, companies with longer operating histories may have established more robust financial reporting systems and governance structures. Controlling for firm age helps account for variations in financial reporting quality that may be attributed to the cumulative industry experience of the companies (Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020).

Also, the size of the board can influence governance dynamics within a company. Larger boards may have different communication channels, decision-making processes, and levels of oversight. Controlling for board size helps ensure that any observed effects of board financial expertise on financial reporting quality are not simply reflections of the board's overall composition.

Despite the ever-increasing importance of board financial expertise (Li & Wahid, 2018), previous research has overlooked carrying out studies on this matter (Dhaliwal, et al., 2010; Aier, et al, 2005; Krishnan, & Visvanathan, 2008 and Huang, & Kisgen, 2013). This study is timely and relevant for several reasons. First, boards and their committees are facing major challenges regarding a variety of financial issues due to the unprecedented risks, volatility and changes in business environments (Deloitte 2020; EY 2020; KPMG 2021). Therefore, this study aims at examining the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality in listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

The following null hypotheses are formulated and tested:

H₀₁: Board financial expertise has no significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Firm size has no significant effect in moderating the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

This study emphasizes the vital role of transparent and reliable financial reporting in Nigeria's listed oil and gas firms. It explores the impact of board financial expertise on reporting quality, acknowledging the historical context of financial scandals. The research introduced firm size as a novel moderating variable which addresses the gap in understanding variations within the oil and gas industry. Control variables like firm age and board size enhance internal validity. The formulated null hypotheses provided a structured framework for testing the direct effect and moderation of board financial expertise on financial reporting quality.

The significance of studying "Board Financial Expertise and Financial Reporting Quality of Listed Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria Moderated by Firm Size" lies in its potential to enhance corporate governance and financial transparency within a critical sector of the Nigerian economy. Board financial expertise is crucial for ensuring accurate and reliable financial reporting, which is fundamental for maintaining investor confidence and achieving regulatory compliance.

2. Literature Review

Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting quality involves providing information about a company's activities and expected cash flows to shareholders (Verdi, 2006). It emphasizes fair and authentic financial statements that reflect the true financial position and performance of the company (Tang et al., 2008). High-quality financial statements offer genuine insights into economic performance, financial position, and cash flow operations, building trust among shareholders and stakeholders (Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2013). Assessing financial reporting quality can be done directly or indirectly. Financial reporting quality refers to the reliability, accuracy, and relevance of information presented in financial statements. It ensures a faithful representation of a company's financial position, performance, and cash flows. High-quality financial reporting involves transparency, completeness, and adherence to accounting standards and regulatory requirements (Oyedokun, & Balogun, 2022).

In this study, financial reporting quality refers to the reliability, accuracy, and relevance of information presented in financial statements, ensuring a faithful representation of a company's financial position, performance, and cash flows, with high quality involving transparency, completeness, and adherence to accounting standards and regulatory requirements.

Board Financial Expertise

Expertise refers to specialized skills or knowledge acquired through training, study, or practice. In the context of board expertise, it refers to directors possessing industry-relevant skills or knowledge. Directors with deep expertise are expected to be more independent and fulfill their strategic role effectively. They contribute to the firm's performance by providing

guidance and advice to management based on their expertise (Hillman & Dalziel, 2003; Krause et al., 2013). Therefore, a board comprising experienced directors from diverse occupational backgrounds becomes an asset for the firm. Board financial expertise refers to the knowledge, skills, and experience related to financial management and decision-making that board members possess. Directors with financial expertise play a crucial role in overseeing financial health, providing guidance, and making informed decisions.

The operational definition adopted in this study defined board financial expertise as the knowledge, skills, and experience related to financial management and decision-making that board members possess, playing a crucial role in overseeing financial health, providing guidance, and making informed decisions.

Firm Size

The concept of firm size has been defined diversely in the literature, encompassing factors such as total assets, operational scale, and the number of employees, among other metrics. The presumption is that larger firms possess more extensive resources, providing them with the capability to allocate these resources across various investment opportunities. Athanoglou et al. (2005) contend that an increase in company size correlates with improved bank performance, while Almajali et al. (2012) argue that the size of a firm can influence its financial performance. However, in the case of exceptionally large firms, the impact of size may turn negative, attributed to bureaucratic complexities and other reasons (Yuqi, 2007).

The significance of firm size in determining its overall value cannot be understated. Larger firms are inclined to exhibit a higher value than their smaller counterparts, evident in their larger scale of operations. This expanded operational capacity is expected to contribute to superior performance compared to smaller firms, especially when the value of a firm is measured in terms of its performance. Many companies actively seek to expand the size of their business operations to foster growth, whether in terms of revenue, the number of employees, or the size of their facilities (Pervan & Visic, 2012; Oyedokun, & Balogun, 2022).

Firm Age

The term "age" is defined as "the time of life at which some particular qualification, power, or capacity arises or rests" (Merriam-Webster, 2019). In the context of a firm, age is often

defined as "the number of years since incorporation" according to Ilaboya and Ohiokha (2016). However, there is debate regarding whether listing should be the defining moment for a firm's age, with some arguing that listing is more economically significant and marks the commencement of a firm's life (Shumway, 2001). Conversely, others reject this perspective, asserting that a firm is legally born through its incorporation as a legal entity (Götzmann, 2008).

Wang (2011) offers an alternative definition, conceptualizing firm age as the number of years elapsed from the establishment of the enterprise to the point under investigation. In cases where the enterprise concludes its operations at the investigation point, Wang suggests that it can also be referred to as the life span of the enterprise. The varying perspectives on how to define firm age highlight the nuanced considerations involved in determining a meaningful starting point for assessing the temporal dimension of a company's existence.

Board Size

Board size is defined as the number of members comprising a firm's board (Panasian et al., 2003). The determination of an optimal board size that positively influences its operational effectiveness has been a topic of debate in scholarly literature (Dalton et al., 1999; Hermalin & Weisbach, 2003). Despite the absence of specific legislative directives detailing the required number of directors for board size, Section 2.1 of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018) mandates that the board should be adequately sized to efficiently carry out its responsibilities. This includes overseeing, monitoring, directing, and controlling the company's activities, with due consideration for the scale and complexity of its operations. The argument in favour of a larger board size is rooted in the belief that it offers a broader reservoir of expertise. Advocates posit that larger boards are more likely to possess a greater array of knowledge and skills, enhancing their capacity to fulfil their duties effectively.

Review of Empirical Studies

In this section, the relationship between the independent variable, board financial expertise, and the dependent variable, financial reporting quality, is examined.

Hussaini and Idris (2014) examine the influence of these monitoring characteristics (e.g Board financial expertise) on financial reporting quality of Listed Conglomerates Firms in Nigeria. The study covers the period of six years 2009 to 2014. Data for the study were

extracted from the firms' annual reports and accounts. After running the OLS regression, a robustness test was conducted for validity of statistical inferences, the data was empirically tested. Francis et al. (2005) model was used in extracting the discretionary accruals of the sampled firms. A multiple regression was employed to test the model of the study using OLS regression Model. The results from the analysis revealed that Board financial expertise is negatively significantly related to financial reporting quality of Listed Conglomerates Firms in Nigeria. provide valuable insights into the relationship between board financial expertise and financial reporting quality in Nigerian conglomerates, the study's counterintuitive findings, limited generalizability, reliance on discretionary accruals as a proxy, and lack of detailed robustness checks warrant further investigation and methodological refinement.

Suleiman et al. (2020) investigated the effect of board attributes (board expertise) on financial reporting quality of the twenty (20) listed consumer goods firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period 2013 to 2018. Samples of thirteen (13) companies were selected using census techniques after applying two filters. The study uses Ex-post facto research design, panel data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of the population studied. The Ordinary Least square (OLS) Model Regression was used in testing the hypotheses stated. Findings showed that board expertise was statistically significant and positively related to financial reporting quality at 5% level of significance, thus, it implies any increase in the amount of expertise in the board will lead to an increase in the financial reporting quality of consumer goods companies. The study focuses on a specific sector (consumer goods firms) and uses a well-defined sample with clear selection criteria. The use of panel data and OLS regression adds robustness to the analysis. The finding that board expertise positively influences financial reporting quality aligns with existing literature, reinforcing the importance of knowledgeable boards. However, the sample size is relatively small (13 companies), which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study covers a relatively short period (2013-2018), which might not capture longer-term trends or effects.

Enebi et al. (2023) investigated the impact of board of directors (financial expertise) and institutional investors on financial reporting quality of Nigerian non-financial listed enterprises over the period 2012 to 2021. The research utilized a sample of 53 businesses, representing a population of 112 firms. To assess the dependent variable, discretionary

accruals, the Modified Jones Model, as outlined by Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeny (1995), was employed. The study employed an ex-post facto research design and collected secondary data from annual reports and accounts. For data analysis, multiple regression analysis was the primary statistical method used during the descriptive phase. The findings from the fixed effect regression analysis revealed a positive and significant relationship between the financial expertise of the board and the quality of financial reporting. While the study employs multiple regression and fixed effect regression analysis, it would benefit from a detailed discussion of potential confounding factors and robustness checks. Additionally, the study could enhance its findings by exploring sector-specific variations within the non-financial firms.

Shamaki et al. (2023) examine the impact of board composition (board expertise) on the degree of financial reporting quality of consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2016 and 2021. Samples of thirteen businesses were selected after using two filters. The study employed an ex post facto methodology, and secondary data were extracted from the population's annual reports and accounts. Regression utilising the Ordinary Least Square Model was used to test the hypotheses. An increase in the number of specialists on the board will help consumer goods companies' financial reporting because it was discovered that board expertise is essential and positively correlated with financial reporting quality. While Shamaki et al. (2023) effectively demonstrate the positive correlation between board expertise and financial reporting quality in consumer goods companies, the study's limited sample size and focus on a single sector may constrain the generalizability of the results, highlighting a need for broader and more diverse samples in future research.

Theoretical Review

In this study, the theory that underpin this study is a signaling theory. Originally proposed by Spence in 1973 to explain information asymmetry in labor markets which has been widely adopted by accounting researchers to understand why companies disclose specific information in their annual reports (Raffournier, 1995; Haniffia & Cooke, 2002; Watson et al., 2002; Akhtaruddin et al., 2009). According to Morris (1987), signaling is a prevalent phenomenon in markets characterized by information asymmetry, and the theory

demonstrates how this asymmetry can be reduced by providing information that serves as a signal to others.

This study posits that companies with boards comprising directors who possess strong financial expertise can effectively signal positive attributes to stakeholders, including investors, lenders, and regulators. The presence of such expertise indicates that the board has the capacity to oversee the financial reporting process and ensure the accuracy and reliability of financial statements. External stakeholders interpret the presence of board financial expertise as a credible signal of the company's commitment to transparent and high-quality financial reporting practices. It signifies that the company is more likely to provide accurate and unbiased information, thereby reducing information asymmetry and bolstering investor confidence.

Additionally, board members' financial expertise can have a positive impact on internal controls, risk management, and overall corporate governance. Directors with financial acumen possess the ability to critically assess financial reports, identify potential issues or inconsistencies, and actively contribute to financial decision-making processes. Their involvement helps uphold the integrity of financial reporting and minimizes the risk of fraudulent practices. Overall, signalling theory suggests that companies with boards comprising individuals with strong financial expertise are more inclined to exhibit higher-quality financial reporting.

3. Methodology

The study adopted a longitudinal research design, which involve collecting data from the same individuals or groups over an extended period. This design enables researchers to study changes or developments over time, assess trends, and examine cause-and-effect relationships. Data were collected from a sample comprised of 10 listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria and covered a period of 20 years (2003-2022), using the firm financial reports, as Board financial expertise was measured based on the qualifications, experience, and professional certifications of board members.

Table 1

Populations and Sample Size

S/N	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE
1	Arдова Plc	Arдова Plc
2	Capital Oil Plc	Capital Oil Plc
3	Conoil Plc	Conoil Plc
4	Eterna Plc	Eterna Plc
5	Japaul Gold & Ventures Plc	Japaul Gold & Ventures Plc
6	Mrs Oil Nigeria Plc	Mrs Oil Nigeria Plc
7	Oando Plc	Oando Plc
8	Rak Unity Pet	Rak Unity Pet
9	Seplat Energy Plc	Seplat Energy Plc
10	Total Energies Marketing Nigeria Plc	Total Energies Marketing Nigeria Plc

For this study, moderating model was adapted from the study of Khan, and Ahmed (2020). The model shows the direct and indirect effect of board independence on financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study specified the models as:

$$FRQ=f(BFE, FAGE, FSIZE) \text{ -----}$$

---(1)

$$FRQ=f(BFE, FAGE, BFE*FSIZE, FAGE*FSIZE, BSIZE*FSIZE) \text{ -----}$$

---(2)

Equation 1 and 2 maintains their structure as a linear regression model, but it introduces an interaction term involving the independent variables and the moderating variable. The association between the independent variables and the dependent variable is now dependent on the level of the moderating variable. The coefficient β_4 serves to measure both the size and direction of this interaction effect. This model is adapted from the research conducted by Faozi et al. (2022).

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BFE_{it} + \beta_2 FAGE_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 FSIZE_{it} + \mu_{it} \text{ -----}$$

---(3)

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BFE_{it} + \beta_2 FAGE_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BFE_{it} * FSIZE + \beta_5 FAGE_{it} * FSIZE + \beta_6 BSIZE_{it} * FSIZE + \mu_{it} \text{ -----}$$

----(4)

Where as:

FRQ = Financial Reporting Quality. In this study, the assessment of financial reporting quality was conducted using the discretionary accruals Model. The model employed discretionary accrual as a proxy to gauge financial reporting quality. Discretionary accruals, as a measure, allow for the identification of accounting choices that may reflect the quality of financial reporting.

$$TACC_{it}/A_{it-1} = \alpha(1/A_{it-1}) + \beta_1[(\Delta REV - \Delta REC)/A_{it-1}] + \beta_2[(PPE_{it})/A_{it-1}] + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

TACC = Total Accruals (NI – OCF)

ΔREV = Change in Revenue

ΔREC = Change in Receivable

PPE = Property, Plant and Equipment

A_{it-1} = Year-end assets for company I in year t-1

ϵ_{it} = error term/residual

BFE = Board Financial Expertise

FAGE = Firm Age

BSIZE= Board Size

FSIZE = Firm Size

BFE* FSIZE = a predictor for firm size-moderated board financial expertise

FAGE* FSIZE = a predictor for firm size-moderated firm age

BSIZE* FSIZE = a predictor for firm size-moderated board size

β_0 = Intercept term (a constant)

β_1 - β_6 = Coefficients of the independent variables.

Based on the model specification and the choice of the variables used in the model, the table below provide the definition, measurement and sources of variables.

Table 2

Variables, Definition, Measurement and Sources

S/N	Variables	Definitions	Measurement	Source
1	Dependent Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ)	This is defined as the faithfulness of information conveyed in the financial reporting process.	Measured by use of modified Jones Model	Modified Jones (1995)

2	Independent Board Financial Expertise (BFE)	Means the directors having special skill or knowledge of accounting and finance	Proportion of the board of directors with accounting and financial expertise to total number of Board members	Moses et al (2018)
3	Control Firm Age (FAGE)	The number of years of incorporation of the company; even though some believe that listing age, should define the age of the company	Number of years passed after listed	Sadiq and Mohammed (2017); (Shumway, 2001).
4	Control Board Size (BSIZE)	Board size refers to the number of members on the board of a firm.	Total number of directors on the board of directors of the company	Ozcan & Riza (2016), Gurmeen (2015), Dabor (2015), Abata and Migiro (2016)
5	Moderating Firm Size (FSIZE)	Firm Size: Refer to the total assets, scale of operations and number of employees among others in an organization	Natural log of total assets	Nwanna and Ivie(2017), Babalola(2013), Badara(2016), Ilaboya & Ohiokha(2014), Dioha et al.(2018), Usman & Amran(2015)

Source: Field Work 2024

4. Results and Discussions

This section discusses the results from analysis of descriptive statistics and panel regression analysis. The discussion begins with descriptive statistics where measures of centrality and dispersion were discussed. Next, regression assumptions were checked and reported, and finally, regression analysis results were presented.

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FRQ	200	.215	.07	.018	.367
BFEXP	200	.089	.042	.013	.398
BSIZE	200	10.295	2.506	6	21

FAGE	200	34.555	16.326	0	67
FSIZE	200	8.808	2.237	2.832	14.878
BFEXPFSIZE	200	.767	.381	.086	2.476
BSIZEFSIZE	200	90.205	28.87	25.486	178.54
FAGEFSIZE	200	310.318	185.951	0	922.455

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for financial reporting quality. The mean FRQ of 0.215 suggests an average level of reporting quality, while the standard deviation of 0.07 indicates variability. Companies should strive for consistency and improvement in financial reporting to enhance transparency. The mean of 0.089 indicates a relatively low average financial expertise on boards, with a standard deviation of 0.042 signifying variability. Firms may benefit from enhancing board members' financial skills to improve reporting quality.

The mean of 10.295 suggests an average board size, and the standard deviation of 2.506 indicates variability. Companies should consider optimizing board size to balance effective governance without excessive complexity. The mean age of 34.555 suggests moderate average firm age, with a wide standard deviation of 16.326 indicating diversity in firm ages. Firms with longer histories may need to ensure ongoing adaptability in financial reporting practices.

The mean of 8.808 represents an average firm size, and the standard deviation of 2.237 indicates variability. Companies need to recognize the impact of size on reporting quality and tailor financial reporting processes accordingly. The interactions between BFEXP and FSIZE, BSIZE and FSIZE, and FAGE and FSIZE reveal mean values (0.767, 90.205, and 310.318) and standard deviations (0.381, 28.87, and 185.951), indicating the average effects and variability in these predictors. Firms should be mindful of these interactions, recognizing the potential influence of firm size on the relationships between financial expertise, board size, and firm age in the pursuit of enhanced reporting quality.

Table 4

Matrix of Correlations

Correlation Probability	FRQ	BFEXP	BSIZE	FAGE	FSIZE
FRQ	1.000000				
BFEXP	-0.471557	1.000000			
BSIZE	-0.172788	0.158763	1.000000		
FAGE	-0.038917	0.032732	-0.093033	1.000000	
FSIZE	0.344504	-0.098463	0.214592	-0.123393	1.000000
	0.0004	0.3297	0.0320	0.2213	

Source: Field Work 2024

The table 4 displays correlation coefficients and associated probability values for the variables FRQ, BFEXP, BSIZE, FAGE, and FSIZE. It reveals that FRQ has a perfect positive correlation with itself, always equal to 1.000000. BFEXP shows a moderate negative correlation with FRQ (-0.471557), which is statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). There is no significant correlation between BFEXP and BSIZE (0.158763) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.1146$). Similarly, BFEXP has no significant correlation with FAGE (0.032732) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.7465$). Although a weak negative correlation exists between BFEXP and FSIZE (-0.098463), it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.3297$).

For BSIZE, there is no significant correlation with FRQ (-0.172788) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.0856$). Additionally, no significant correlation is observed between BSIZE and BFEXP (0.158763) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.1146$). Similarly, BSIZE has no significant correlation with FAGE (-0.093033) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.3572$). While a weak positive correlation is present between BSIZE and FSIZE (0.214592), it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.0320$). FAGE does not exhibit a significant correlation with FRQ (-0.038917) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.7007$). Furthermore, there is no significant correlation between FAGE and BFEXP (0.032732) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.7465$). Similarly, no significant correlation is found between FAGE and BSIZE (-0.093033) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.3572$). Additionally, FAGE does not show a significant correlation with FSIZE (-0.123393) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.2213$).

In the case of FSIZE, there is a moderate positive correlation with FRQ (0.344504), which is statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). However, there is no significant correlation between FSIZE and BFEXP (-0.098463) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.3297$). While a weak positive correlation exists between FSIZE and BSIZE (0.214592), it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.0320$). Furthermore, no significant correlation is observed between FSIZE and FAGE (-0.123393) at a conventional significance level ($p = 0.2213$). These correlation coefficients provide information about the strength and direction of relationships between the variables. Positive correlations indicate variables that tend to move together, while negative correlations suggest variables that move in opposite directions. The magnitude of the correlation coefficient indicates the strength of the relationship, with values closer to 1 representing a stronger correlation. The associated probability values (p-values) indicate the statistical significance of the correlations. Lower p-values indicate more reliable and significant correlations.

Table 5

Panel Regression results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.034656	0.06941	-0.499288	0.6188
BFEXP	0.875299	0.361333	2.422417	0.0175
FAGE	0.006646	0.001423	4.671629	0
BSIZE	-0.014118	0.003705	-3.810884	0.0003
BFEXP_FSIZE	0.116559	0.032709	3.563536	0.0006
BSIZE_FSIZE	-0.001126	0.000328	-3.430759	0.0009
FAGE_FSIZE	0.000405	8.26E-05	4.895432	0
Root MSE	0.032719	R-squared		0.867308
Mean dependent var	0.157092	Adjusted R-squared		0.849006
Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.604646	F-statistic		47.38799
Durbin-Watson stat	1.624431	Prob(F-statistic)		0

Source: Field Work 2024

The given table 5 presents the results of a regression analysis. The R-squared value is 0.867308, indicating that the independent variables in the regression model explain approximately 86.7% of the variation in the dependent variable. The F-statistic is 47.38799, which tests the overall significance of the regression model. A higher F-statistic with a low probability (p-value) suggests that the model is statistically significant and provides a good fit to the data. The Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.624431, which tests for autocorrelation in the residuals. A value between 1.5 and 2.5 suggests no significant autocorrelation.

The coefficient for the variable board financial expertise is 0.875299. This indicates that a one-unit increase in board financial expertise is associated with an average increase of 0.875299 units in the dependent variable. The t-statistic for board financial expertise is 2.422417, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.0175$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable. The coefficient for the variable firm age is 0.006646. This implies that a one-unit increase in firm age is associated with an average increase of 0.006646 units in the dependent variable. The t-statistic for firm age is 4.671629, indicating that the coefficient is statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable. The coefficient for the variable board size is -0.014118. This indicates that a one-unit increase in board size is associated with an average decrease of 0.014118 units in the dependent variable. The t-statistic for board size is -3.810884, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.0003$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

The coefficient for the variable board expertise when moderated by firm size is 0.116559. This indicates that a one-unit increase in board expertise when moderated by firm size is associated with an average increase of 0.116559 units in the financial reporting quality. The t-statistic for board expertise when moderated by firm size is 3.563536, indicating that the coefficient is statistically significant ($p = 0.0006$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable. With regard to first and second hypotheses, these results are inconsistent with the results of Farber (2005), Ditropoulos and Asteriou (2010) but is according to the results of Petra (2007), Bradbury et al. (2006), Ahmed and Duellman (2006), and Vafeas (2000). As to institutional ownership, the result is inconsistent with the result of Shama (2006).

The coefficient for the variable board size when moderated by firm size is -0.001126. This indicates that a one-unit increase in board size when moderated by firm size is associated with an average decrease of 0.001126 units in the dependent variable. The t-statistic for board size when moderated by firm size is -3.430759, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.0009$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable. The coefficient for the variable firm age when moderated by firm size is 0.000405. This implies that a one-unit increase in firm age when moderated by firm size is associated with an average increase of 0.000405 units in the dependent variable. The t-statistic for firm age

when moderated by firm size is 4.895432, indicating that the coefficient is statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). This suggests that the coefficient has a significant effect on the dependent variable. The results found here are in accordance with the outcome of Charles et al., (2018) that detailed a positive significant influence of firm size on financial reporting in the study of Nigeria consumable goods firms.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between board independence and the financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. In conclusion, Board Financial Expertise before moderation emerges as a significant positive predictor, indicating that an increase in board financial expertise is associated with an improvement in financial reporting quality. In contrast, the findings indicate that the presence of firm size as moderating variable, board financial expertise exerts a negative and statistically significant impact on financial reporting quality. It suggests that, in larger firms, the positive effect of board financial expertise on financial reporting quality may be mitigated or even reversed. This could prompt a reassessment of governance structures or strategies for larger companies.

Based on these findings, the study recommended the following:

- i. Organizations should prioritize recruiting and retaining board members with relevant expertise and knowledge in financial reporting. This can be achieved by seeking individuals with strong financial backgrounds, accounting qualifications, and experience in regulatory compliance.
- ii. Given the moderating effect of firm size, it is important to consider the unique characteristics and challenges associated with different company sizes. Larger firms may require boards with more diverse expertise to effectively handle complex financial reporting requirements, while smaller firms may benefit from specialized expertise in specific areas.
- iii. Board members should engage in ongoing professional development programs to stay updated with evolving financial reporting standards, regulatory changes, and best practices. This will help enhance their expertise and ensure they are equipped to make informed decisions related to financial reporting quality.

- iv. Establishing robust governance mechanisms, such as regular board evaluations, independent audits, and clear reporting lines, can contribute to improving financial reporting quality. These practices help ensure accountability, transparency, and adherence to reporting standards.
- iv. Continuously monitor and evaluate financial reporting quality using relevant metrics and benchmarks. This allows organizations to identify areas for improvement, assess the effectiveness of board expertise, and make necessary adjustments to ensure high-quality financial reporting.

References

- Abata, M. A., & Migiro, S. O. (2016). Corporate governance and management of earnings: Empirical evidence from selected Nigerian listed companies. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 13(2), 189 – 205.
- Akeju, J. B., & Babatunde, A. A. (2017). Corporate governance and financial reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, 4(2), 3749-3753.
- Akhtaruddin, M., Hossain, M. A., Hossain, M., & Yao, L. (2009). Corporate governance and voluntary disclosure in corporate annual reports of Malaysian listed firms. *Journal of Applied Management Accounting Research*, 7(1), 1–19.
- Asegdew, K. (2016). Determinants of financial reporting quality: Evidence from large manufacturing share companies of Addis Ababa. May, 1–83.
- Ashafoke, T., Dabor, E., & Ilaboya, J. (2021). Do CEO Characteristics affect financial reporting quality: An Empirical Analysis. *AUDOE*, 17(1), 156-176.
- Badara, M. S. (2016). The moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between board structure and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Sahel Analyst: Journal of Management Sciences*, 14(3), 101-115.
- Badolato, P Denelson DC, & Ege M (2013). Audit committee financial expertise and earnings management: The role of status, 1-76.
- Dabor, A. O., & Dabor, E. L. (2015). Audit committee characteristics, board characteristics and financial reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, United Kingdom, 3(11), 1292-1304.

- Dechow, P. M., Sloan, R. G., & Sweeney, A. P. (1995). Detecting earnings management. *The Accounting Review*, 70(2), 193–225.
- Enebi, K. D., Nuraddeen, U. M., Abdullahi, M. (2023). Board of directors, institutional investors and financial reporting quality: evidence from listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 12(1), 55-69.
- Fathi, J. (2013). Corporate governance system and quality of financial information. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(2), 129-142.
- Fung, B. (2014). The demand and need for transparency and disclosure in corporate governance. *Universal Journal of Management*, 2(2), 72-80.
- Haniffa, M. and Cooke, E. (2002). Culture, corporate governance and disclosure in Malaysian Corporations. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business Studies*, 38(3), 317-349.
- Hillman, A. J., & Dalziel, T. (2003). Boards of directors and firm performance: Integrating agency and resource-dependence perspectives. *Academy Management Review*, 28(3), 383–396.
- Hussaini, B., & Idris, I. (2014). Monitoring characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed conglomerates firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting Research and Practice*, 3(2), 75-93.
- Ilaboya, O. J., & Ohiokha, O. (2014). Board independence and financial statement fraud: the moderating effect of female gender diversity. *Accounting & Taxation Review*, 1, 196-221.
- Ivanova, I. A., & Bikeeva, M. V. (2016). Corporate social responsibility: specificity, formation mechanism, estimation of management efficiency. *European Research Studies*, 19, 167.
- Jones, J. (1995). Earnings management during import relief investigations. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 29(2), 193-228.
- Klai, N., & Omri, A. (2011). Corporate governance and financial reporting quality. The case of Tunisian firms. *International Business Research*, 4(1), 158-166.
- KPMG. (2021). The Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018. Retrieved from <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ng/pdf/advisory/2018-Nigerian-Code-ofCorporate-Governance.pdf>
- Mahboub, R. (2017). Main determinants of financial reporting quality in the Lebanese banking sector. *European Research Studies Journal*, XX(4B), 706-726
- Markham, J. W. (2015). A financial history of the United States: From Enron-era scandals to the subprime crisis (2004-2006) from the subprime crisis to the Great Recession (2006-2009). Routledge.

- Martinez, F. J, Garcia, S. I. M. &, Cuadrado, B. B. (2013). Effect of financial reporting quality on Sustainability information disclosure. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 22(1), 45-64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1330>.
- Moses, T., Ofurum, C. O., & Egbe, S. (2018). Audit committee characteristics and quality of financial reporting in quoted Nigeria banks. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 2(5) 1-10.
- Nyor, T. (2013). Financial reporting quality of Nigerian firms: Users' perception. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(13), 273-79.
- Ogundajo, G.O., Odunayo, J., Osunsusi, A.K., Desi, A. & Oyedokun, G.E. (2023). Digitalized Accounting System: Revamping Small and Medium Enterprises Financial Reporting System. *The American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (THE AJHSSR)* 6(30), 99-113. www.theajhssr.com DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56805/ajhssr>
- Ojo, L. O., Oyedokun, G. E., & Fodio, M. I. (2020). Effect of audit committee characteristics on financial reporting quality of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Uniben Journal of Accounting*. 4(1), 12-27. A publication of the Department of Accounting, University of Benin.
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Balogun, A. I. (2022). International Financial Reporting Standards and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *AFAR Multidisciplinary Journal of Management Sciences (MJMS)*. 4(3), 27-56. A Publication of The Association of Forensic Accounting Researchers (AFAR).
- Oyedokun, G.E., Okwuosa, I., & Isah, S (2019). Effect of audit characteristics on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods company in Nigeria. *Fountain University Osogbo Journal of Management (FUOJM)*, 4(3), 161-180. A Publication of Departments of Accounting & Finance and Business Administration, Fountain University, Osogbo. www.osogbojournalofmanagement.com Available at <http://osogbojournalofmanagement.com/index.php/ojm/article/view/132/108>.
- Rasha, B. (2017). Main determinants of financial reporting quality in the Lebanese banking sector. *European Research Studies Journal*, 20(4b), 706-726.
- Shamaki, A. R., Shehu, U. H., & Saidu, A. (2023). Effect of board attributes on financial reporting quality of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Path of Science*, 9(8), 3001-3009.
- Soheilyfar, F., Tamimi, M., Ahmadi, M. R., & Takhtaei, N. (2014). Disclosure quality and corporate governance: Evidence from Iran. *Asian Journal and Finance and Accounting*, 6(2), 75-86.
- Suleiman, S., Jamilu, B., & Jamilu, M. (2020). Board attributes and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Jalingo Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 2(2), 55-67.
- Tang, Q., Chen, H., & Lin, Z. (2008). Financial reporting quality and investor protection: A Global Investigation. *Working Paper, University of Western Sydney, Shanghai University of Finance and Economics, Hong Kong Baptist University*.

- Tiamiyu, M. A., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Public sector auditing and integrity of government financial reporting in Nigeria. International Conference of Public Administration, Department of Public Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi November 18- 20, 2019
- Usman, A. B., & Amran, N. A. (2015). Corporate social responsibility practices and corporate financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria companies. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 11(4), 749-763.
- Verdi, S. (2006). *Financial reporting quality and investment efficiency*. A dissertation submitted to the department of accounting and financial, University of Pennsylvania.
- Waddah K. H. O., Khaled, S. A., Mohd 'Atef M D. Y., & Mohamad, H. S. (2020). The associations of board of directors' characteristics with modified audit opinion. *AD-minister, Enero – Junio*, 37, 5-34.